

FINGER MILLET VARIETIES

A well managed finger millet field

Drying finger millet

PESE 1:

Plant height - 100 cm
Days to mature - 100
Yield - 2500-3000 kg/ha
Colour - Brown

SEREMI 1:

Plant height - 85-90 cm
Days to mature - 90
Yield - 2500-3000 kg/ha
Colour - Light Brown

SEREMI 2:

Plant height - 85-90 cm
Days to mature - 75-80
Yield - 1850-2000 kg/ha
Colour - Dark brown/Maroon

SEREMI 3:

Plant height - 90 cm
Days to mature - 85
Yield - 2300-2500 kg/ha
Colour - Brown
Where to get seed
National Semi-Arid Agricultural Research Institute
(NASARRI), Serere and authorized agro input dealers.

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CLUSTER GRANARY SEED PROJECT NaSARRI

Finger Millet Production Guide

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Introduction

Finger millet is an important cereal and staple food of much of eastern, northern and western Uganda. Storability and high nutritive value of the grain, as well as drought tolerance, make this crop a suitable cereal for food security in the dry lands.

Land preparation

The fields should be well prepared early enough free from large sheds of trees and anthills. Dig (plough) the plot and harrow twice to make the soil soft before start of rains.

Seed rate

The seed to be planted should be uni-form in color and size. the seed rate is 5-10 kg/ha. Seed should be dressed with Thiram-Lindane (Fernesan D).

Planting /sowing

Plant in rows at the start of the rains by:- Making furrows spaced at 1 ft (30 cm) apart. In the furrows apply uniformly Compound NPK 20:20:0 fertilizers (one 50 kg bag/acre). A handful should go 10 steps (10 m) along the furrow. If you cannot afford fertilizer, plant with manure. In the furrows put uniformly very little seed (1 kg per acre). A handful of seed should plant 100 steps. Cover the furrows with loose soil.

Weeding

Do first weeding 2 weeks after emergence. Do second weeding 2 weeks after first weeding and thin in the rows so that 1 plant is 1 hand (15 cm) away from the other.

Pests

Normally very free of pest attack, as the crop is the first to germinate in the main growing areas, it attracts attacks from Army worms, Locusts, Qui-lea birds, rodents, and grasshoppers. Storage pests include: Rats, ants and to some extent web worms and the brown beetles

Diseases

Blast (*Pyricularia grisea*), may produce irregular seed setting in severe attack especially in wet years. Seed dressing helps in control. Other diseases are of minor importance and include leaf spot, Tar spot, virus disease complex.

Harvesting

By hand with small knives, it is laborious. Can be harvested by machine. Select heads for next year's seed before main harvesting begins.

Storage

After thorough sun-drying up to about 13% moisture level, it is sored un-threshed or is threshed and stored in gunny bags. Finger millet is free from serious storage pest attack. Storage pests include: Rats, ants and to some extent web worms and the brown beetles.

Yields (threshed)

Good yields will be more than 1,700 kg/ha. Loss on drying panicles is about 40%. Threshing percentage is 75-80%.

